

Ramanujan's Tau-Function and Convolution Sums

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Abstract:

We study certain type of convolution sums involving an arbitrary arithmetic function f , which is applied to Ramanujan's tau function when f coincides with the sum of divisors function.

Keywords: Convolution sums, Sum of divisors function, Ramanujan's function $\tau(n)$, Niebur's formula, Lanphier's identity.

Introduction

We shall study convolution sums with the structure:

$$S_g^{(r)}(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n k^r g(k) g(n-k), \quad r, n \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

where g is an arbitrary arithmetic function, in particular:

$$S_g^{(0)}(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n g(k) g(n-k), \quad S_g^{(1)}(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n k g(k) g(n-k), \quad (2)$$

then with the Z-transform (Grove, 1991; Patra, B. (2018), it is easy to prove the identity $n S_g^{(0)}(n) = 2 S_g^{(1)}(n)$, that is:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (n-2k) g(k) g(n-k) = 0. \quad (3)$$

In Sec. 2 we use (3) to obtain the Lanphier's identity involving convolution sums of the form (1), and we show how to generalize his identity. In Sec. 3 we employ the mentioned Lanphier's expression to simplify the Niebur's formula for the Ramanujan's tau function.

Lanphier's Identity

The arithmetic function g is arbitrary, then in (3) we can employ $g(n) = n f(n)$, to obtain:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (n - 2k) k (n - k) f(k) f(n - k) = \sum_{k=0}^n (2k^3 - 3n k^2 + n^2 k) f(k) f(n - k) = 0, \quad (4)$$

that is:

$$2 S_f^{(3)}(n) - 3n S_f^{(2)}(n) + n^2 S_f^{(1)}(n) = 0, \quad (5)$$

in complete agreement with Lanphier (Lanphier, 2004; Gallardo, 2010).

Similarly, in (3) we use $g(n) = n^2 f(n)$ to deduce the property:

$$2 S_f^{(5)}(n) - 5n S_f^{(4)}(n) + 4n^2 S_f^{(3)}(n) - n^3 S_f^{(2)}(n) = 0, \quad (6)$$

and for the general case $g(n) = n^r f(n)$:

$$\sum_{j=r}^{2r} (-1)^j \binom{r}{j-r} n^{2r-j} \left[2 S_f^{(j+1)}(n) - n S_f^{(j)}(n) \right] = 0, \quad r \geq 0, \quad (7)$$

which is equivalent to (1) of Gallardo(2010).

Niebur's Relation for $\tau(n)$

If f is the sum of divisors function, then the Niebur's formula (Gallardo, 2010; Ewell, 1984; Wikipedia, n.a.) for the Ramanujan's tau function (Ramanujan, 1916; Roy, 2017):

$$\tau(n) = n^4 \sigma(n) - 24 \sum_{k=0}^n k^2 (35 k^2 - 52 k n + 18 n^2) \sigma(k) \sigma(n - k), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (8)$$

can be written in the form:

$$\tau(n) = n^4 \sigma(n) - 24 \left[35 S_\sigma^{(4)}(n) - 52 n S_\sigma^{(3)}(n) + 18 n^2 S_\sigma^{(2)}(n) \right], \quad (9)$$

where it is possible to employ the identity (5) obtained by Lanphier (2004) to deduce:

$$\tau(n) = n^4 \sigma(n) - 24 \left[35 S_\sigma^{(4)}(n) - 60 n^2 S_\sigma^{(2)}(n) + 26 n^3 S_\sigma^{(1)}(n) \right], \quad (10)$$

$$= n^4 \sigma(n) - 24 \sum_{k=0}^n k (35 k^3 - 60 n^2 k + 26 n^3) \sigma(k) \sigma(n - k). \quad (11)$$

Remark.-From (8) are immediate the following congruences of Ramanujan (1920):

$$\tau(j n) \equiv 0 \pmod{j}, \quad j = 2, 3, 5, 7, \quad (12)$$

and the result of Ewell (1984):

$$\tau(n) \equiv \begin{cases} 0 & \pmod{8}, \quad n \text{ even,} \\ \sigma(n) \pmod{8}, & n \text{ odd.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

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